

TRENDS IN THE MODERNIZATION OF PLOVDIV AND PAZARDZHİK AGGLOMERATION AREAS INTO INNOVATIVE ECONOMIC CENTERS AND SMART CITY

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ABSTRACT

This article focuses on the need to develop agglomeration areas through innovative development and the imposition of the model of smart settlements. The purpose of these development policies is to achieve the integration of information and communication technologies, use of human and social capital to improve the quality of life of citizens and achieve sustainable economic development. The focus of the article predetermines the need for the settlements of the Plovdiv-Pazardzhik agglomeration area to achieve a high level of intelligent management. Through the introduction of electronic management, user-oriented administrative services are implemented, and the convenience and safety of electronic services are implemented in every way. Fostering collaboration between the public and private sectors and city dwellers is key to developing smart citizens who will be engaged and empowered to make positive contributions to their cities and communities.

KEYWORDS: model, information, intelligent management, integration, regional, areal

ABSTRAKT

Dieser Artikel befasst sich mit der Notwendigkeit, Ballungsräume durch innovative Entwicklung und die Einführung des Modells der intelligenten Siedlungen zu entwickeln. Das Ziel dieser Entwicklungspolitik ist die Integration von Informations- und Kommunikationstechnologien, die Nutzung von Human- und Sozialkapital zur Verbesserung der Lebensqualität der Bürger und eine nachhaltige wirtschaftliche Entwicklung. Im Mittelpunkt des Artikels steht die Notwendigkeit, dass die Siedlungen des Ballungsraumes Plovdiv-Pazardzhik ein hohes Maß an intelligenter Verwaltung erreichen. Durch die Einführung der elektronischen Verwaltung werden nutzerorientierte Verwaltungsdienstleistungen implementiert und der Komfort und die Sicherheit elektronischer Dienstleistungen in jeder Hinsicht umgesetzt. Die Förderung der Zusammenarbeit zwischen dem öffentlichen und privaten Sektor und den Stadtbewohnern ist der Schlüssel zur Entwicklung intelligenter Bürger, die sich engagieren und befähigt werden, einen positiven Beitrag zu ihren Städten und Gemeinden zu leisten.

STICHWORTE: Modell, Information, intelligente Verwaltung, Integration, regional, räumlich

RÉSUMÉ

Cet article se concentre sur la nécessité de développer les zones d'agglomération par le biais d'un développement innovant et de l'imposition du modèle des établissements intelligents. L'objectif de ces politiques de développement est de parvenir à l'intégration des technologies de l'information et de la communication, à l'utilisation du capital humain et social afin d'améliorer la qualité de vie des citoyens et

de parvenir à un développement économique durable. L'objet de l'article est de déterminer la nécessité pour les établissements de la zone d'agglomération de Plovdiv-Pazardzhik d'atteindre un niveau élevé de gestion intelligente. Grâce à l'introduction de la gestion électronique, des services administratifs orientés vers l'utilisateur sont mis en place, et la commodité et la sécurité des services électroniques sont mises en œuvre de toutes les manières possibles. La promotion de la collaboration entre les secteurs public et privé et les citoyens est essentielle pour développer des citoyens intelligents qui seront engagés et habilités à apporter des contributions positives à leur ville et à leur communauté.

MOTS-CLÉS: modèle, information, gestion intelligente, intégration, régional, local

INTRODUCTION

Modernization goes through the introduction of new technologies and their management in order to create a new labour market that will bring new occupations and new industries to the forefront of the 21st century economy. According to leading experts in urban studies, the development of cities is conditioned on the development of urbanism as the platform and smart cities are some of the trends in engagement cities in digital [Petrov, 2021]. This predetermines that, in addition to the ongoing processes of modernization and optimization of the level of urban development in cities and their areas, the application of the smart city model is required. Thus, according to the understanding of the European Parliament, the idea of a smart city means the development and integration of information and communication technologies, the use of human and social capital to improve the quality of life of citizens and to achieve sustainable economic development. This approach also has a dedicated Digital Europe (2021-2027). programme, which focuses on the digital future. According to its contents, the main priority areas are supercomputing, artificial intelligence, cyber defence, advanced digital skills, etc. Cities and urbanized areas in the Asenovgrad-Plovdiv-Pazardzhik direction are specific territorial formations that are characterized by a high degree of dynamism in development and variability over a relatively small distance. These are the territories carrying the growth, concentrating the main growth factors - human resources, investments, technologies, etc. On the other hand, these growth generators are also the source of the manifestation of social and economic problems in a concentrated form on small territories [Vassileva, 2018]. These characteristics of cities make them a kind of priority in regional policy. Thus, in practice, the modernization of urbanization between Plovdiv and Pazardzhik goes in search of innovative solutions in the field of connectivity, infrastructure, ecology, shared resources, transport, energy, education, etc. Which in practice means the need for an integrated type of territorial management based on the practical-applicational field of innovation and modern technologies. In this direction, it is necessary for the territory to have the necessary level of intelligent specialisation. The authors Lyubomirova and Tsolov define smart specialization as an approach to regional development guided by the strengths of the region/territory/urban agglomeration/municipality [Lyubomirova and Tsolov, 2022]. This approach should of course build on the In this context, the design of regional strategies and policies should take into account analyses of the level of development of the region between Pazardzhik and Plovdiv, which can be expressed through a number of elements of economic potential, but can also be expressed through analyses of the overall competitiveness of the region (as measured by the degree of qualification of the territory) or the competitiveness of the regional supply of goods and services. Given that a region can be defined by the interaction of its structure, behaviour and functionality within a general system, we can consider the region as a complex subsystem characterised by a series of specific or common variables.

These variables can be input or set variables, state variables characterizing the behavior of the subsystem at a given time or over a given period, and output or set variables [Georgiev, 2022]. Between these variables, which can be grouped according to certain criteria, there are a number of relations and relationships, causal or functional relationships. The development of the functional nature of regional development can be argued by laying down a model of the Plovdiv-Pazardzhik mega-agglomeration area, which should strive for a smart city model. Through this aspiration, the Asenovgrad-Plovdiv-Pazardzhik area is able to successfully solve the multitude of public problems through solutions based on the latest technologies and through partnerships between citizens, academic organizations, businesses, municipalities and public administration. When talking about such a large spatial area, at least six "smart or intelligent" dimensions are usually mentioned: economy, mobility, environment, lifestyle, people and urban governance. These dimensions are manifested through the model of "sharing economy". This economy has already begun to underpin the business models embedded in modern cities, and knowledge is gradually becoming the most valuable capital and growth factor of any modern city. The smart city or municipality uses information and communication technologies to increase operational efficiency, share information with the public, and improve the quality of government services and the well-being of citizens.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Planning and development of innovative development and smart villages. Planning focused on urban design as a means to develop healthy cities and smart living. A positive trend in this direction is the creation of a common tourism product first with municipalities such as Plovdiv, Velingrad, Panagyurishte from the South Central region offering rural, ecological, hunting, fishing tourism (Pazardzhik), urban, cultural and congress tourism (Plovdiv) and spa and balneo tourism (Velingrad). This shows that the development of individual industries helps to develop the Asenovgrad-Plovdiv-Pazardzhik agglomeration area with its subsystems for creating smart living - smart home, provision of basic services, education, health security, culture and tourism (standard of living). With a modern smart economy dominated by small and medium enterprises, green technologies and jobs, innovative local industry and business (competitiveness). Imposing in the Asenovgrad-Plovdiv-Pazardzhik area a smart environment achieving emission reduction, green and open spaces, green buildings with efficient use of natural resources, water management, waste management, disaster risk management (sustainability). Also smart mobility - environmentally friendly modes of transport such as cycling, pedestrian access, alternative fuel vehicles, reducing congestion, providing logistical information (connectivity). Achieving high levels of smart energy through renewable energy resources, energy efficiency, smart grids, smart meters, fuel cell energy storage (energy efficiency). Enforce the educated people model with modern local schools for human and social resources, universities, schools, business communities, adolescents, social integration, social cohesion (knowledge). Last but not least, imposing in the Plovdiv-Pazardzhik area a model of smart governance that rests on a mechanism of communication between local government and residents of e-government, open data centers with transparent data, community consultation (participation).

In this direction, it is necessary to work to achieve social cohesion and reduce regional disparities in the social sphere by creating conditions for human capital development. This involves drawing up a balanced territorial development by strengthening the network of urban centres, improving connectivity

in the regions and the quality of the environment in the settlements [Evrev, 2018]. In this direction, the construction of the Kableshkovo Intermediate Terminal between Plovdiv and Pazardzhik is important. The aim is to free the road network from heavy loads and to develop rail transport. The terminal is co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund through the Operational Programme Transport. It is located on an area of 71 450 sq. m. in the area of Todor Kableshkov railway station and is part of Plovdiv railway junction. It is built on the route of the Kalotina-Sofia-Plovdiv-Dimitrovgrad-Svilengrad railway, part of the European corridor connecting Europe and Asia. The distance from Pazardzhik to Plovdiv along the railway line will be covered in less than 20 minutes at a speed of 160-200 km/h. This will ensure the movement of passengers and freight in this section much faster. Modern communication and telecommunication has been built, which ensures a good level of security.

Another important project is the creation of an urban railway in the direction Asenovgrad - Plovdiv Airport - Plovdiv - Pazardzhik. This will be done by building three rings, the first is the construction of the main ring of the urban railway, the second - the construction of connections to individual settlements, and the third ring will serve the settlements in the direction Plovdiv - Stamboliiski - Pazardzhik - Septemvri. The first ring will have 13 stops will have the city railway station of Plovdiv - railway station Asenovgrad, Mavrudovo, Krumovo (crossing to airport Plovdiv), Southeast industrial zone (in the area of the former plant "Piščešišti stroje"), Central railway station Plovdiv, Pehstersko shoe (in the area of the store Kaufland), bul. "Sixth of September (in the area of the station "Пловдив"), District Hospital, Filippovo railway station, Industrial zone Voyvodino (industrial zone), Skutare (industrial zone), Ravadinovo, Benkovski. The second ring will connect the municipalities of Plovdiv, "Rodopi", "Maritsa", Asenovgrad and Kyklön and has a chance to be the first railway in the country. The third ring is to create conditions for this railway to be joined by the Plovdiv-Peshtera and Plovdiv-Pazardzhik lines by including a number of smaller settlements in order to create effective connectivity in the Asenovgrad-Plovdiv-Pazardzhik agglomeration area.

The modernization of Plovdiv Airport could also be an important project. Investments in Plovdiv airport are necessary, especially after the increasing interest in the airport from aviation operators and low-fare airlines that are entering the country as a result of the liberalisation of the air transport sector after EU membership. The passenger terminal at Plovdiv Airport meets passenger service standards but needs upgrading and further strengthening of its capacity. At present, Plovdiv Airport is in the process of developing its customer portfolio, placing the most significant emphasis on the expansion of the aviation route network. The aim is not only to increase the volume of flights during the active winter season, taking into account the period of transformation of the aviation business, but also to attract year-round scheduled flights. At the same time, we believe that the professional support of the tourism industry and the local authorities will be necessary to build a quality and effective marketing strategy for the development of aviation services at Plovdiv Airport. Achieving these goals will inevitably lead to the promotion of other business opportunities for us, expansion of commercial non-aviation activities, attraction of new partners and [Yovcheva, 2012].

The construction of the South-Eastern Bypass of Plovdiv /from the Karaulkata of Plovdiv to Skobeleva Maika/ and the South-Western Bypass of Plovdiv /the old Ring Road to the Trakia Highway/ is of great importance for the connectivity to Plovdiv Airport and other settlements to it. A structural determinant for the economy of the region and the state is also the enterprise "KCM" JSC, which together

with the developing economic zones "Trakiya" and "Maritsa", where the automotive parts factories are being built at an accelerated pace, define Plovdiv as a center for serious investments. All this contributes to the increase in freight and passenger traffic on the existing road network, which is almost at capacity. The design gauge of the section from the Skobeleva Mama junction to the roundabout with Asenovgradskoe Shose should be G20. The road will thus be classified as an expressway with a maximum speed of 120 km/h. One is for drainage and hydraulic calculations of trenches and the other is for an overpass over the Burgas railway at km 102+115.02 (railway km 161+050). After the completion of the south-eastern ring road (Route II-56 "Brezovo - Plovdiv - Route II-86", section from km 90+000 to km 102+820), it will be possible for freight traffic to reach the newly built intermodal railway terminal near Plovdiv.

Important for the agglomeration area Pazardzhik-Plovdiv is also the construction of the Western bypass of Pazardzhik, which will start at km 123 of the secondary road II-37 Panagyurishte - Pazardzhik - Peshtera before the northern entrance of the town of Pazardzhik /from Panagyurishte/ and will end at km 128+900 of the secondary road, before the village of Glavinitsa. With the construction of the bypass, the heavy traffic coming from the Trakia motorway will move out of the town centre. This will increase traffic safety for commuters by avoiding entering the district town. There will be four major facilities on the Western Bypass of Pazardzhik. It is planned to build a bridge over an irrigation canal and an overpass over the railway line Sofia - Plovdiv. A new right lane will be built on the bridge over the Maritza River, and the existing left lane, built in 1995-96 and 205 m long, will be rehabilitated. The other major structure on the bypass is an existing bridge over a drainage channel. In the longer term, a project for the design and construction of an eastern bypass from the I-8 main road to the II-37 secondary road around Pazardzhik should be considered. Construction of local lanes on the main road I-8 in the section from the town of Pazardzhik. Pazardzhik to the village of. Malo Konare". Also construction of local lanes on Second class road II-37 in the section from Pazardzhik to the Trakia motorway junction.

Another important aspect is the experience in the Plovdiv-Pazardzhi agglomeration area to develop new technologies leading to competitive advantages and increasing the added value of national products and services in the field of healthy living industry and biotechnologies. The healthy living and biotechnology industry in the field of plant science is developing rapidly in the Plovdiv-Pazardzhik area. In recent years, the HORIZON 2020 project "PlantaSyst" has been implemented by the Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology - Plovdiv (IMBB) and partners.

The potential for rural tourism and traditional handicrafts remains untapped, as does the creation of a common tourism product for the South Central Region offering sightseeing, rural, ecological, hunting and fishing tourism (Pazardzhik municipality), urban and cultural tourism (Plovdiv municipality) and spa and wellness tourism (Velingrad, Bratsigovo, Rakitovo municipalities, etc.). In general, in the area of Pazardzhik-Plovdiv there is a need to improve the capacity of local entrepreneurship to apply for EU operational programmes, which would provide good funds for modernisation, especially in the sectors of agriculture, textiles and tourism.

Modeling of industrial zones in agglomeration area of Plovdiv- Pazardzhik. The industrial zones are also important for the development of the Plovdiv-Pazardzhik agglomeration area. There are several zones located in the area. The leading one is the Thrace Economic Zone (TIZ), which is an industrial-commercial zone in the Plovdiv area and one of the largest economic projects in Bulgaria. The TIZ covers

a total area of 10 700 000 m², of which 3 250 000 m² are built-up. The zone comprises six industrial zones around Plovdiv, where projects worth over EUR 1 billion have been implemented by Bulgarian and foreign companies. As of 2015, the TIZ employed over 30,000 people. The Rakovsky Industrial Zone was created through a public-private partnership in Rakovsky was born in Italy when the then mayor of Rakovsky, Franz Kokov, visited the country's economic zone together with a business delegation. A few months later, the Municipality of Rakovski organised an auction for 815 acres of municipal land. The bid was won by the Plovdiv construction company "Syenit". The company has experience in the construction of factories, having previously built production facilities in the Maritsa zone near the Plovdiv village of Radinovo. Other zones are Industrial and Commercial Zone Kuklen, Agrocenter Kaloyanovo, High Technology Innovation Park Trakia, Educational and High Technology Park-Plovdiv and Industrial and Commercial Zone Maritsa. The important significance of these industrial zones is that they will promote the regional development of the Plovdiv-Pazardzhik agglomeration mainly in two directions - first, thousands of new jobs will be created for highly and low-skilled personnel from Plovdiv and the region. And secondly - the presence of large investors means that gradually in the city and surrounding municipalities will develop companies from small and medium-sized businesses as subcontractors and suppliers at the local level, are categorical representatives of business and state institutions. Once large companies enter the zone, they are joined by their partners and supporting industries, thus creating the backbone of small and medium-sized businesses [Kolev, 2008]. Economic zones can be developed and expanded, which will lead to even better opportunities in the logistics sector. Very soon, much better developed rail transport will also be available. This will shorten the supply route, which is currently a major problem. There is also the concept of carbon neutrality in the last mile of deliveries. This includes plans to build buffer depots in the periphery and rely only on electric transport in the centre. For example, the Thrace Economic Zone has even more ambitious plans for carbon neutrality. It is planned that 45% of the energy used in the zone will come from renewable sources in 2025, 60% in 2030 and full neutrality will be achieved in 2040. In the "Thrace Economic Zone" it is planned to build an "EU-China New Economy Cooperation Pilot Zone - Plovdiv" - an innovative public platform for business, logistics, finance, direct connection between consumer and producer, for online and offline trade. This comprehensive platform, bringing together the markets of Asia and Europe, aims at price competitiveness of goods and higher turnover [Kalinkov, 1999].

The food industry is important for the Plovdiv-Pazardjik area. This sector has a wide production specialization - meat processing, dairy processing, fruit and vegetable processing (canning), milling, production of confectionery, beer, soft drinks, cigarettes and others. The development of the sector is linked to the favourable opportunities provided by the city as a market for production and the availability of suitable raw material resources. The food industry is the leading industry in the Plovdiv region, accounting for around 30% of total production in the region. The industry has the highest relative share in the production of food products, beverages and tobacco products, which account for 24.4% of the net revenues of the industry in the region. In addition, the essential oil processing industry is highly developed on the territory of the Plovdiv-Pazardzhik area. Large and smaller companies engaged in similar activities [Kalinkov and Kalchev, 2007]. Due to its favourable geographical location and well-supplied infrastructure, the extraction and processing of essential oils in the district is extremely well developed and provides opportunities for intensive production processes in line with the application of the latest technologies in

this industry. Companies involved in medical and pharmaceutical activities and manufacturing are also strongly represented, accounting for about 14.4% of the net industry revenues in the region.

The development of economic spatial clusters (zones) in the Plovdiv-Pazardzhik area is the other fragment leading to competitive advantages and increasing the added value of products and services in the field of new technologies in all sectors of the economy. The focus is in the direction of imposing new innovations and practices [Kalinkov and Kalchev, 2007]. In this direction, a number of pilot projects are being implemented in the municipality of Plovdiv. A case in point is the implementation of the Smart Parking Meter concept, which uses an app to help drivers find available parking spaces without a lengthy detour through crowded city streets. A step in this direction is its full application in the municipalities of Plovdiv and Pazardzhik, where paying for parking in the city centre is also possible via SMS. In transport, smart traffic management involves monitoring and analysing flows in order to optimise the operation of streetlights and to prevent congestion on roadways based on busy times. In Plovdiv and Pazardzhik, since 2017, a "Traffic Management Center" has been operating, in order to achieve optimal traffic control, the intersections in Plovdiv are divided into separate groups, which in different parts of the city are managed by different methods, namely:

- By synchronizing the traffic lights on the main avenues and the traffic in the different time zones, a green wave is provided in certain directions;
- for single intersections in the city, an own automatic control cycle is achieved by traffic detectors;
- the dispatch centre for the control and management of urban bus routes ensures a better quality of service for citizens.

Smart cities also need smart governance. By implementing e-government, the user is put at the centre of administrative services, taking all possible measures to achieve convenience and security when using electronic services [Lyubomirova and Tsolov, 2022]. It promotes: the effectiveness and efficiency of services by increasing the return on investment, creating an environment of administrative accountability and transparency in the provision of e-services and in the decision-making process, enhancing user confidence in e-security and improving the protection of their data and rights in a digital environment. The main objective of smart digital technologies in the field of state and municipal government is to increase the share of residents receiving state and municipal services electronically. E-government requires not a literal electrification of existing administrative services, but a complete re-engineering of work processes. This implies that all administrations should model their administrative service processes with the aim of moving towards providing them automatically and electronically [Mladenov, C., E. Dimitrov, 2009]. The proven effects of e-government are the reduction of the administrative burden for citizens and businesses, the simplification and streamlining of administrative workflows in the provision of administrative services, service-oriented automated data and information exchange that "follow" the user, fully electronic document exchange that reduces document turnover and eliminates the risk of document loss/destruction, etc. With the national e-ID scheme in production mode, the user becomes identifiable to the systems and receives electronic administrative services efficiently and effectively. This means that administrations collect the data, information and evidence they need ex officio and, by providing services based on automated processes, orient the results of administrative services towards the user. National e-government policies are conducive to the development of cross-

border e-services that citizens and businesses need when travelling, working, studying or doing business within the EU[Mehandjiev and Ovcharova, 2013].

Smart public transport in smart cities, provides public transport that meets consumer demand. Smart transit companies coordinate services and meet citizens' needs in real time, improving efficiency and making them as convenient and efficient as possible. The project "Plovdiv Intelligent Transport Systems" implemented by the Traffic Management Center for a total cost of BGN 6,223,620 including VAT as part of Plovdiv's major transport project has its difficulties and satisfactory sustainability. On the other hand, a traffic management system including new traffic controllers with advanced technology, traffic detectors at strategic locations, traffic light displays and devices including a system for giving priority to buses serving the mass public transport, CCTV system at specific locations, sub-systems and equipment for the traffic management centre were constructed and implemented within the project. Adjustments were made at 50 intersections to provide an accessible environment for the public, including people with disabilities[Mladenov and Dimitrov, 2010].

Bicycle rental is a possible public service in a smart city that saves time, money and emissions. In this respect, a 48-kilometre bicycle lane network has been built in Plovdiv through the Operational Programme Regional Development (OPRD) 2007-2013, which has contributed to a significant increase in the number of citizens opting for the greener alternative transport. And since 2021, through a memorandum of cooperation between the Municipality of Plovdiv and a private company, citizens can use environmentally friendly transport, namely electric scooters. Due to the excellent results and appreciation of the citizens, in 2023 an electric bicycle system is expected to be operational.

Let us not forget the implementation of innovative technologies in tourism. The unique history and modern atmosphere of Plovdiv and Pazardjik make them a popular tourist destination for over 800,000 foreign tourists and Bulgarians every year. A modernization for easier access and targeting of tourists is the introduced "City Card" program. City Card is a digital platform that allows tourists to visit museums, galleries and other attractions, as well as places to eat and have fun, for free or at a discount, using their digital card called Plovdiv City Card. In less than a year, the Plovdiv City Card has helped increase tourist traffic to key sites by 10% - especially museums, galleries and tours, through a platform that has worked equally well for tourists and the municipal enterprise. The digitised Plovdiv City Card product also helped drive attention and traffic to the city through targeted marketing efforts and content. The smart city concept is increasingly being used to improve public safety by monitoring high crime areas and improving emergency preparedness with sensors. Smart sensors can be critical components of an early warning system before natural events such as earthquakes, floods, landslides or hurricanes.

Smart buildings are also part of the One Smart City project. The introduction of digital smart technologies in construction and housing and utilities is an important prospect to increase the efficiency of the design, construction and operation of real estate sites, to ensure high-quality planning of settlements, housing and services provided in the housing and utilities sector, and to increase market transparency for end users. Existing infrastructure can be upgraded and new buildings built with sensors that not only provide real-time space management and ensure public safety, but also monitor the structural health of buildings. Attaching sensors to buildings and other structures can detect wear and tear and notify officials when repairs are needed. Citizens should be proactive and notify officials, via a smart city app, when repairs are needed to buildings and public infrastructure such as potholes. Sensors

can also be used to detect leaks in water mains and other pipe systems, helping to reduce costs and improve efficiency for public workers. Smart city technologies also contribute to the efficiency of urban production and urban agriculture, including job creation, energy efficiency, space management and fresher goods for consumers. Smart city initiatives must involve the people they aim to support: residents, workers and visitors [Nikolov, 2016]. City leaders must not only raise awareness of the benefits of smart city technologies being implemented, but also promote the use of open and democratized data for their citizens. If people know what they are participating in and the benefits they can contribute, they are more likely to engage and become active in the creation of such cities. Fostering collaboration between the public and private sectors and city residents is the key to creating a smart citizenry that will be engaged and empowered, and will contribute positively to the city and community. New and innovative methods of collaboration can improve engagement. Smart city projects should include plans to make citizen engagement transparent and accessible, often through an open data portal or mobile app. This allows residents to engage with the data and understand what it is being used for and what is being done. Through the smart city app, residents can also perform personal tasks, such as monitoring their home energy consumption, paying bills and finding efficient public transport(13). In this respect, the municipality of Plovdiv is implementing a system from the beginning of 2023 that will allow passengers to charge with mobile apps, debit and credit cards. In this way, there will be a much greater control over compliance with public transport timetables.

Of course, there are also risks in smart cities, such as city managers not maintaining data privacy and security, possible exposure of the data that citizens produce on a daily basis, risk of hacking or misuse. The presence of sensors and cameras could be perceived as an invasion of privacy or as government surveillance. To prevent this, city data collected should be anonymized and not be personal information.

Resilience is a key aspect of smart cities... In this direction, the cities of Plovdiv and Pazardzhik could think about more fully deploying the use of IoT-enabled sensors and cameras to monitor the cleanliness of public spaces, the density of moving people and the movement of locally registered cars. Its smart technologies will help companies and residents monitor energy use, production waste and water use in real time. For example, Narrowband IoT (NB-IoT) technology could make inroads in Plovdiv and Pazardzhik. It is a technology standard that connects a wide range of devices, machines and services using cellular telecommunication technologies. The main advantages of the technology are lower device costs, longer battery life, better indoor coverage, optimized data transmission, two-way communication, low latency, high connection security and quality of service. The air monitoring solution detects pollution and particulate levels, and also measures temperature and humidity. The system is applicable for indoor and outdoor spaces and the information is monitored using a web-based application. With the solution, municipalities will have real-time information on air quality. The smart waste management service is suitable for municipalities and waste collection companies. With the help of sensors, it automatically identifies how full the garbage containers are. The system offers automated route calculations and navigation based on information analysis and also offers a garbage collection report to customers [Petrov, 2009]. Its use saves time resources and financially can reduce up to 70% of garbage collection costs. The smart lighting system uses LED modules to optimise the control of street lights, automatically adjusting the degree of illumination throughout the day. The modules are compatible with existing lighting poles and are easy to adapt. The use of smart lighting using Narrowband IoT technology improves living

conditions in urban areas and reduces annual costs by up to 25%. The Narrowband IoT smart parking solution detects available parking spaces, enables online parking space reservation, automatically determines the shortest route to the available space and performs cashless transactions in pay zones. The system performs centralised monitoring, taking into account parking trends, occupancy rates and violations. Its implementation improves the occupancy of parking spaces by up to 25% and increases the collection of revenue from violations by up to 20% per year in all settlements of the Plovdiv-Pazardzhik agglomeration. Plovdiv is also thinking about the gradual enforcement of autonomous vehicles, which are complemented by smart bus stops that provide free Wi-Fi, USB charging stations and bus information updates for citizens. A bike sharing program and a smart parking app that includes online payment options are also available. At the same time, building a smart municipal agency will also allow Plovdiv and Pazardzhik to actively use sensors to monitor temperature, pollution and noise, as well as monitor humidity and rain levels, regulate traffic and more.. For example, the implementation of smart bulbs in Plovdiv and Pazardzhik are used to increase the energy efficiency of street lighting, and increasingly the home, which can help to protect the home, turn an ordinary light switch into a dimmer, and much more. Some of these bulbs require a one-time purchase of a small control hub, which must be plugged into the current and control up to 50 of these smart bulbs. Smart doorbells allow one to see who is outside the home even when we are not home, using a camera that allows a connection to the person at the door. When someone rings, the host receives a video call on the phone. He can answer or completely ignore the call, and if he has a smart lock he can even open without being in his home. Most popular smart security devices use a motion detector to notify when someone is at the door. More and more companies are investing in developing innovative building materials that help builders around the world build homes that use less energy. Plovdiv has joined the General Assembly of the European Innovation Partnership on Smart Cities and Communities, or EIP-SCC for short. In practice, the EIP-SCC is one of five important tools to create a common European smart city market, focused on energy, mobility and integrated infrastructures and engaging with all sectors and all scales to create and ensure a growing, open and inclusive market. This initiative is starting to attract from across Europe representatives of the main market leaders to work together and want to offer integrated solutions leading to the growth of this market. But at the moment, smart city business models are severely hampered by factors such as a lack of public funds to cover the full investment [Petrov, 2021]. Also the way of outsourcing, the value system of the society and the increasing participation of the society in financing - e.g. crowdfunding, social media, etc. These factors create needs and opportunities for innovation in the Plovdiv-Pazardzhik agglomeration to develop and implement new approaches to manage and return on investments made in infrastructure and services. These changes affect all stakeholders, who need convincing evidence of the value and viability of using new business models. Active work with young people and the creation of employment opportunities is offered by the Centre for Social Innovation at the Municipality of Plovdiv. It is the first of its kind in Bulgaria and aims to reduce unemployment and bring young people back into public life. The Centre works with people between 15-29 years of age, and an important condition is that they are not engaged in employment, education or training. Its main goal is to unite all the services of the Municipality of Plovdiv at a single point of contact and thus facilitate young people in their contact with companies, organizations and foundations looking for employees, workers and/or trainees.

CONCLUSION

All initiatives and activities in innovative development will enable the Plovdiv-Pazardzhik area to gain experience that will allow for wider access to the European Union structural funds in order to be able to use these funds to attract and stimulate private investment through the application of appropriate and innovative business models and hybrid financing. There is also a need for a change in the attitude of investors and the way of dealing with them. Most investors characterise smart city investments as relatively small, too slow and too risky, and this is the case at this stage. A change in the mindset, expectations and way of working with private investors is needed, which means using appropriate business models and strengthening public-private partnerships. The city market is becoming one of the largest in the world, private investors cannot miss it just because it is more complex. To make this market attractive for direct investment, work needs to be done to reduce investment risk by increasing investor confidence in the return on investment in urban projects. This means involving the investment community early in the preparation and structuring of deals, ensuring knowledge transfer, building innovative commercial capabilities and innovative business processes in cities. Controlling diversity - applying standards Globally, the creation of smart cities is already in a 'maturity' phase and it is quite understandable that some cities benefit more and others less from the introduction of smart city technologies. The term "smart city" can be used for some world cities, but the opportunities for Plovdiv and Pazardzhik to join this group are not small at all. These cities should have the opportunity to study and apply best practices in creating smart cities and even contribute in testing or collaborating in offering innovations. Because cities like Plovdiv, Pazardzhik and their satellite cities and towns can be more flexible and faster in introducing individual solutions. Thus, through common action and inclusiveness, an extended investment market is created, and within the EU.

Winning over and engaging civil societies is particularly important to ensure higher investor confidence, although it is a process of multiple activities and initiatives at city level. Cities should try to plan the transformation process by setting fundamental smart objectives. In most cases, to achieve these goals and to account for the expected financial, social and environmental outcomes, cities need to make significant changes but public support is needed.

The initiators of the concept must therefore know public attitudes very well, understand them and use them to ensure active public engagement. These are city actions and initiatives that may not be directly visible to the investment community, but which are vital to the development of a smart city. A toolkit is needed to support cities in this endeavour and an example of such a toolkit is the Sofia City of Knowledge Cluster. But increasingly there needs to be an awareness and information campaign to make people understand and realise the essence of the Smart idea and Smart Cities. The concept needs to be embraced by the scientific community developing the ideas and technologies, by investors and implementers of smart solutions, by city governments, but also by the citizens using and living in these cities Citizens should feel free and comfortable, have security, but also space to develop their own qualities and creativity. In contrast to the above objective conditions, the Plovdiv-Pazardzhik agglomeration area has a very good potential for accelerated socio-economic development, determined also by the good condition of the settlement network - good infrastructure development, connectivity and accessibility of the territories, positive development of the social sphere and human resources, good

ecological condition, excellent geographical characteristics and the presence of numerous natural resources, rich history and cultural heritage.

Good interaction between local and central authorities with proven opportunities for the use of EU funds and programmes, etc. are factors which in the medium term create preconditions for calming internal and external migration processes, ensuring higher employment and income levels, higher natural population growth and balancing regional disparities. Thus, the improving state of the settlement network is one of the favourable preconditions for a balanced and sustainable development of the local community. Partnership frameworks should be intensified and diversified with innovative measures, necessarily including digital transformation of the public sector for the benefit of larger community groups, contributing to making information a key asset and improving digital connectivity. Digitalisation at the service of citizens and businesses and effective partnerships for resource sharing ensure the quality functioning of the Plovdiv-Pazardjik area in every partnership.

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